

Supplemental Information

Implicating the Cholecystokinin B Receptor in Liver Stem Cell Oncogenesis

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Primer Name	Sequence 5' to 3'	Primer type
oIMR6447	CTT AGC CTG GAC AGA GAA GC	Common
oIMR6916	CTT GGG TGG AGA GGC TAT TC	Mutant forward
oIMR7283	CCA AGC TGC TGG CTA AGA AG	Wild type Forward

Table S1. Primer sequences used to genotype mice and establish a colony of wild type, heterozygous, or CCK-BR-KO mice.

Study Name	Diet	Mechanism of CCK-BR	Study Assessments
Study A Prevention- DDC diet injury	0.1%DDC & Standard Chow	Pharmacologic- proglumide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biochemical • Histology • Flow cytometry • 3-D Spheroids propagation • Cytokine Array • RNA Sequencing
Study B Reversal- DDC diet injury	0.1%DDC & Standard Chow	Pharmacologic- proglumide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of diet • Biochemical • Histology
Study C Transgenic, DDC diet injury	0.1%DDC	Genetically engineered Wild type (CCK-BR ^{+/+}) Heterozygous (CCK-BR ^{+/-}) Knockout (CCK-BR ^{-/-})	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biochemical • Histology • 3-D Spheroids propagation • RNA Sequencing
Study D Transgenic, CDE diet injury	75% CDE & Standard Chow	Wild type & CCK-BR-KO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biochemical • Histology • Flow cytometry • 3-D Spheroids propagation

Table S2. Description of the four separate studies performed.

Figure S1. Animal study designs of the four separate experiments. *A:* Study A, Prevention-Pharmacologic DDC study in wild type mice: In this study, N=40 male mice were divided into 2 cohorts of N=20 mice each. One cohort was fed the 0.1% DDC diet and the other cohort was fed standard chow. Half of the mice in each cohort (N=10) were provided drug-free drinking water and the other half (N=10) were treated with proglumide water proglumide (0.1mg/ml). *B:* Study B, Recovery study: The sixty mice in this study were divided into four groups: two control groups were fed a standard mouse diet (Lab Diet 5001), and two DDC groups were fed a 0.1% DDC-supplemented diet for 6 weeks and followed by a recovery period of 5 weeks with standard mouse diet. Half of the mice in each group were given either untreated drinking water, while the other half received water supplemented with proglumide (0.1mg/mL). *C:* Study C, Transgenic, genetically engineered murine experiment was conducted with 3 cohorts: wild type C57BL/6 mice (N=8), CCK-BR heterozygous mice (N=6), or CCK-BR-KO mice (N=6) all fed the 0.1% DDC diet for 4 weeks. *D:* Study D, NASH-inducing 75% CDE diet with three cohorts (N=10 mice each): wild type C57BL/6 mice fed fed standard chow, C57BL/6 wild type mice fed the CDE diet, and CCK-BR-KO mice fed the CDE diet.

Figure S2. Food intake and mouse body weight. A: Food intake for each group in Study A of the prevention, DDC-injury model using pharmacologic treatment with proglumide is shown. B:

Mouse body weights over time in Study B, Prevention, pharmacologic DDC study. *C*: Mean weekly food consumption in grams per group in Study B, the reversal study shows the DDC-fed mice consumed less food until week-7 when they were returned to the standard chow. *D*: Animal weight in grams in the DDC-fed proglumide reversal study B showed significant less weight in the DDC-fed mice through week-6. The mouse weight recovered to baseline and to the same weight as control mice when standard chow was provided during the recovery phase. *E*: Food intake over time in Study C where the genetically engineered transgenic mice were all fed the 0.1%DDC diet compared to wild-type mice on the same diet. *F*: The DDC diet resulted in weight loss in all 3 cohorts of DDC-fed mice of Study C regardless of their genotype. *G*: Mean food intake in CDE-fed mice of Study D compared to control mice over an 8-week period. *H*: Mean mouse body weights over time on the CDE diet compared to controls.

Figure S3. Representative ex-vivo livers from each treatment group. The control and proglumide treated mice on standard chow had livers that were normal in color. The DDC-treated mice had darker and firmer livers due to the cholestasis. The mice treated with both DDC & proglumide had darker livers but not as dark as the DDC-alone treated mice.

Figure S4. Liver mass index was calculated for each group. DDC-treated mice had significantly greater liver mass index and this value was lowered by treatment with proglumide. Calculated by one way AVOVA with Turkey test for multiple comparisons.

Figure S5. Representative images from the livers of CDE-fed mice reacted with the CD133 antibody. The CDE diet for 8-weeks also increased the expression of CD133+ stem cells; however, the number of immunoreactive cells was about half that of the DDC-fed mice. *A*: Liver section from mouse on control diet shows minimal CD133+ stem cells. *B*: CD133+ cell number significantly increases in the liver sections of wild type mice fed the CDE diet. *C*: The number of CD133+ immunoreactive stem cells in the liver sections of CDE-fed mice was reduced by 50% in CCK-BR-KO mice. *D*: Analysis of CD133+ stem cells in the CDE-fed mice shows that livers of transgenic CCK-BR-KO mice have less stem cells compared to wild-type mice. Analysis by Student's T-test corrected by Bonferroni for multiple comparisons * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, and *** $P < 0.005$.

Figure S6. Flow cytometry of cells isolated after liver dissociation in wild-type CDE-fed mice and enrichment reveals that 23.6% of the cells are CD133+ (stem cells) and of these 74% express CCK-BR.

Figure S7. Differentially expressed genes implemented in hepatic stem cell activation and HCC affected by treatment with proglumide in DDC-fed mice. *A*: Heat map of relative expression of genes involved in stem cell regulation that are downregulated from RNA sequencing data from DDC-fed wild-type mice treated with proglumide. *B*: Heat map of significantly down-regulated gene expression of transcription factors in livers of DDC-fed mice with untreated H2O compared to that of DDC-fed mice on proglumide. *C*: Heat map of significantly down-regulated RNA expression of cell cycle control genes in livers of DDC-fed mice with untreated water compared to genes from livers if DDC-fed mice treated with proglumide. *D*: Heat map showing up-regulation and expression level of genes associated with HCC progression or HCC biomarkers in livers of DDC-fed mice with or without proglumide. Scale bar in *A*, *B*, and *C*: Depicted in yellow scale is 1.0-fold or 100% expression or dark blue 0-fold or 0% compared to DDC-fed mouse livers with untreated water.

Figure S8. Ingenuity Pathway Analysis proposed regulatory network for DDC mice receiving proglumide treatment shows predicted downregulation of cellular proliferation and oncogenesis. Measured gene downregulation by RNAseq is shown in blue while upregulation is shown in orange. In general, the downregulated E2F transcription factors are central hubs of the proposed gene network, along with other cell cycle genes. Pathway analysis predicted downregulation of cancer initiation, cell proliferation, and tumor formation.